
162. Cosmology with Gaia’s quasars

IN THE EARLY studies of Gaia in the 1990s, we recognised that the large numbers of measurable quasars, of order 500 000 or more, would contribute fundamentally to the determination of the quasi-inertial reference frame (e.g. Bachchan et al., 2016; Klioner et al., 2021).

Today, Gaia’s quasar survey is also being applied to two topical observational questions in Λ CDM cosmology: the kinematic dipole anomaly, and the S_8 ‘tension’ in the amplitude of cosmological structures.

WHILE Λ CDM has passed a vast range of impressive experimental tests, there remain big gaps in the theoretical understanding of its key ingredients, including the nature of dark matter and dark energy, the asymmetry of matter versus antimatter, and whether the dimensionless parameters of physics evolve with time.

Among observational questions are certain discrepancies in the cosmological model parameters inferred from different data sets. Prominent amongst these is the $\sim 5\sigma$ ‘tension’ in the cosmic expansion rate H_0 as measured from the cosmic microwave background compared with more local distance calibrators (essay 44).

There is a similar discrepancy in the value of the dipole amplitude of the cosmic microwave background radiation, and the ‘kinematic dipole’ defined by the distribution and motion of objects on scales approaching the Hubble length (e.g. Rubin & Heitlauf, 2020; Ananthanarayan & Mohanty, 2021; Mohayaee et al., 2021; Peebles, 2022; Lombriser, 2023). It arises as follows.

The amplitudes of the spherical harmonic expansion of the CMB temperature of degree $\ell > 1$ are interpreted as remnants of the decoupling of acoustic oscillations in the early Universe. But the dipole amplitude, $\ell = 1$, is much larger than predicted from this effect, and is instead attributed to the Sun’s motion relative to the CMB of amplitude 370 km s^{-1} in the Galactic coordinate direction $l = 264^\circ$, $b = 48^\circ$ (Aghanim et al., 2020).

Adjusting for the solar motion within our Galaxy, and thereafter for the barycentric motion of the Local Group, implies that the Local Group is moving relative to the CMB at 620 km s^{-1} in the direction $l = 272^\circ$, $b = 30^\circ$.

OBJECTS DISTANT enough that their distribution should approximate to a homogeneous isotropic universe should display a similar dipole anisotropy in their number counts (Ellis & Baldwin, 1984). Early tests at both radio (Baleisis et al., 1998; Blake & Wall, 2002) and X-ray wavelengths (Scharf et al., 2000) have been followed by many similar studies, arguing both for and against a discrepancy (see Peebles, 2022, §3.2.4).

Recent tests have been made using a million quasars from the WISE survey based on their mid-infrared colours (Secrest et al., 2021; Singal, 2021). A joint analysis of various catalogues of radio galaxies *and* quasars concluded that their sky distribution is *inconsistent* with the standard Λ CDM model, at the 5.1σ level, similar to that of the Hubble tension (Secrest et al., 2022).

BUT THE PENDULUM has swung the other way with the construction of the Quiaia quasar catalogue (Storey-Fisher et al., 2023). This merges the 6 649 162 quasar candidates from Gaia DR3 having redshift estimates from its low-resolution BP/RP spectra (Delchambre et al., 2023) with the **unWISE infrared catalogue** (reprocessed from WISE) to construct a large volume spectroscopic quasar sample. It has 1 295 502 quasars with $G < 20.5$ mag, and 755 850 candidates in an even more well-defined sample to $G < 20.0$ mag.

Taking into account selection effects, and especially contamination near the Galactic plane, Mittal et al. (2023) concluded that the Quiaia quasar dipole *is* consistent with the cosmic microwave background dipole, in terms of both amplitude and direction. This lends further support to the Λ CDM model, in the sense that the observed quasar dipole can be attributed to our local departure from the Hubble flow.

ANOTHER EXPLANATION for the cosmic dipolar tension has been given by Cai et al. (2022). They postulate that it originates from a gigaparsec-scale void, whose own existence has been discussed as another observational discrepancy facing Λ CDM (e.g. Peebles, 2022, §4). Evidently, the final word has not yet been written!

IN THE SECOND of these recent applications of the Gaia quasar data to cosmological studies, I will return to a topic that I made passing reference to in essay 161: a study of their angular clustering in order to place constraints on the amplitude and growth of cosmological structure, and to compare these observations with the predictions of Λ CDM cosmology.

This is a contribution to what is referred to as the ‘ S_8 tension’. This is a distinct discrepancy, of around 3σ , in the amplitude of the predicted matter density fluctuations based on the cosmic microwave background data, and the many observations, at low redshifts, inferred from direct measurements of galaxy clustering data, or weak lensing (‘cosmic shear’) data.

Incidentally, the principle of these ‘weak lensing’ surveys is that distant radiation passing massive foreground objects undergoes a deflection whose magnitude depends on the total lensing mass, whether luminous or dark. The deflection distorts the observed shape of extended galaxies, in a manner which is spatially correlated. The mass distributions that cause the lensing can then be constrained from these spatial correlations.

The Gaia contribution that I will discuss here is also based on the Gaia–unWISE all-sky quasar catalogue, Quaia (Storey-Fisher et al., 2023). But let me first explain the context in a little more detail.

THE AMPLITUDE of density fluctuations, of galaxies or clusters, is characterised by this S_8 parameter, defined as $S_8 = \sigma_8(\Omega_m/0.3)^{0.5}$, where σ_8 is the variance of the linear matter overdensity field in spheres with a $8h^{-1}$ Mpc radius, and Ω_m is the fractional energy density of non-relativistic matter, both defined at $z = 0$.

The value of S_8 has been measured by various galaxy clustering and weak lensing surveys, notably from the Dark Energy Survey (Abbott et al., 2018; Troxel et al., 2018), from Subaru (Hikage et al., 2019), and from KiDS (Heymans et al., 2021). These, and a number of others, have resulted in various degrees of ‘tension’ compared with the value inferred from the Planck satellite. The best-constrained cosmic shear data tend to suggest smaller values of S_8 than the Planck value, 0.832 ± 0.013 .

From combined data, García-García et al. (2021) derived $S_8 = 0.7781 \pm 0.0094$, with errors comparable with the Planck CMB measurements, but deviating by 3.4σ . They also reconstructed the *evolution* of S_8 from $z \sim 2$ to the present epoch, and argued that the main contribution to the tension in the measured value of S_8 is due to a lower amplitude of fluctuations than the Planck prediction in the range $z = 0.25 - 0.7$, unfortunately with limited constraints at lower or higher redshifts.

The importance of resolving the S_8 tension is that, if systematic uncertainties in the microwave background or cosmic shear analyses can be excluded, the results may point to new physics giving rise to a slower growth of perturbations at later times (e.g. Adil et al., 2024).

FURTHER CONSTRAINTS, and an extension of the redshift range over which the growth history can be reconstructed, can be derived from quasar clustering measurements, both through three-dimensional analyses of their auto-correlation (Laurent et al., 2017; Castorina et al., 2019; Neveux et al., 2022), as well as their cross-correlation with other tracers.

With this objective, García-García et al. (2021) also considered 343 708 objects with measured redshifts in the range $z = 0.8 - 2.2$ covering 4800 deg^2 from the SDSS–eBOSS survey. But as the sparsest of their clustering samples, it provided limited new constraints.

AND SO to the constraints enabled by the Gaia quasar data, again making use of the Quaia catalogue resulting from the merger of the 6 million quasar candidates from Gaia DR3 with the unWISE infrared catalogue (Storey-Fisher et al., 2023). This large-volume spectroscopic sample, with redshifts, has 1 295 502 quasars with $G < 20.5 \text{ mag}$.

Alonso et al. (2023) examined the angular clustering of the quasars in the Quaia catalogue to derive improved constraints on the amplitude and growth of structure. The main attributes of the Quaia catalogue in this respect are its full-sky coverage, high spatial density, and redshift coverage to $z \lesssim 4$ with good redshift accuracy (e.g. $|\Delta z/(1+z)| < 0.01$ for 62% of the sources). They used the full $G < 20.5$ Quaia catalogue, divided into two redshift bins ($z < 1.47$ centred on $z = 1.0$, and $z > 1.47$ centred on $z = 2.1$) each containing approximately the same number of sources.

This allowed them to constrain the growth of structure over a range of cosmic times, complementary to those accessed by previous analyses, but importantly giving access to significantly larger spatial scales.

There is an important consequence of this broad coverage: since it is usually not possible to fully break the degeneracy between growth and geometry with existing datasets, results are generally reported in terms of the combination $S_8 = \sigma_8(\Omega_m/0.3)^{0.5}$. The large-scale coverage of the Quaia/Gaia sample allows independent estimates of σ_8 and Ω_m , thus providing a constraint on the amplitude of matter fluctuations, $\sigma_8 = 0.766 \pm 0.034$, and on the fractional abundance of non-relativistic matter, $\Omega_m = 0.343^{+0.017}_{-0.019}$, together yielding $S_8 = 0.819$.

THEIR STUDY concluded that the Quaia quasar results are compatible with Planck at the 1.4σ level, and therefore do *not* provide support for the ‘ S_8 tension’. Nevertheless, their higher redshift sample favours a value of σ_8 that is lower than the Planck measurement at the $\sim 2.5\sigma$ level.

Future Gaia releases should give improvements in quasar numbers and redshift accuracy. Meanwhile, we have hints that the Gaia quasar sample has alleviated both the dipole anomaly, and the S_8 tension.